
THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, ITS DESCRIPTION, AND ITS POSSIBILITIES OF APPLICATION IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PHYSICS

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence technologies are currently a rapidly developing language. The rapid development of this technology creates wide opportunities in the field of education, especially in the field of physics. This article presents the concept of artificial intelligence and its possibilities for increasing students' interest in teaching physics in secondary schools.

Keywords: school physics class, artificial intelligence, information technology, Internet, natural sciences.

Introduction. Artificial intelligence is a specific field of computer science that deals with the creation of intelligent machines capable of performing tasks that usually require human intelligence. These tasks include problem solving, speech understanding, decision-making, and learning. SI systems are designed to analyse and interpret data, identify patterns, and make predictions or recommendations based on the collected data. The role of artificial intelligence in education is to enhance the student's learning experience by providing a personalised approach and personalised recommendations. AI-based systems can assess a student's individual strengths and weaknesses, tailor lessons to meet their specific needs, and provide real-time feedback and recommendations. Such a person-oriented approach helps students learn complex concepts more effectively and at a pace suitable for them [1–2].

Scientific research on the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the educational process has been conducted since 2000, and most of them have been studied philosophically, pedagogically, and psychologically.

Currently, in school physics lessons, in the process of forming the scientific and technical worldview of students, in the process of teaching physics, in the process of arming students with scientific and theoretical information and practical skills and qualifications in physics, they have an interest in their profession. The improvement of concepts such as belief and responsibility is considered an important socio-pedagogical phenomenon. Under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on March 19, 2019, to increase attention to young people, to involve them in culture, art, physical education and sports, to teach them

the skills of using information technologies, to promote reading among young people promotion, the adoption of a decision at the meeting on the issue of increasing women's employment and the implementation of a number of works within the framework of ensuring the implementation of this decision, a measure aimed at organizing the effective use of computer technologies and the Internet among the population and young people - as a result of the increasing number of activities, the need for specialists who have the ability to use computer technologies, in particular, the Internet and information communication systems, is increasing day by day, increasing the relevance of our research once again [3-7].

Literature analysis. The philosophical foundations of the problem are expressed in the scientific research works of T.M. Makhmatov, V.A. Lektorsky, V.V. Vdovin, S. Haikin, S. Russell, P. Norvig, J. Barrat, others.

Huang, Y. M. Liang, T. H., Chen, C., Wang, X. and Kong, X. Research on improving student motivation in health sciences including physics by using augmented reality in mobile learning systems. And they used artificial intelligence systems to solve and evaluate physics problems. Kim, Y. J. and Park, J. H. Lar developed an artificial intelligence-based system and investigated how it affects students' scientific creativity and interest in science.

The study of the illumination and research of the research problem in the theory and practice of pedagogy shows that the use of artificial intelligence technologies in education, including teaching physics, has made it possible to effectively solve a number of problems from a methodological point of view [8].

The use of artificial intelligence systems in educational processes creates wide opportunities for improving the quality of teaching and personalizing education. Several examples of the use of artificial intelligence in the teaching process can be given:

- Adaptive teaching. AI-based adaptive learning systems can offer individual learning materials and tasks for students based on information about students, their knowledge and abilities. This allows each student to study at their own pace and get help from the artificial intelligence system.

- Automatic check of assignments. AI can be used to automatically check assignments, including tests, problems, and essays. This helps to save the teacher's time and to quickly re-establish communication with the student. Also, AI gives the student the opportunity to analyze and take into account the mistakes he makes and the student's weaknesses when preparing the next assignments.

- Virtual chat bots. AI-based virtual assistants can be used to communicate with students and provide them with the necessary information and real-time support. Virtual assistants can answer questions, explain rules, remind students of assignments, and make recommendations on the learning process.

- Data analysis and forecasting. AI's ability to easily process large amounts of data allows the teacher and school administration to analyze the dynamics of each student's mastery, the general state of education and training in classes. It can be useful in obtaining data and predicting the educational achievements of students. It helps to make the right decisions about the organization of the educational process and to change it according to the needs of the students.

- Virtual and augmented reality. The use of virtual reality and augmented reality based on artificial intelligence will help to expand educational opportunities and create an effective environment for students.

The main part. Pedagogical scientists in our country have carried out a number of scientific researches on the use of modern information and communication technologies in physics education. However, the problem of using artificial intelligence technologies in teaching physics at school has not been studied as a separate research work.

The use of AI technologies in physics classes can significantly increase the effectiveness of teaching and increase the activity of students' educational activities. Artificial intelligence technologies can be used to create interactive learning applications, simulations, and virtual labs that allow students to conduct physics experiments and explore, and practice the laws of physics. Such programmes can be tailored to the individual needs of each student, allowing them to study at their own pace and focus more on difficult topics.

In the context of physics education, AI can play a crucial role in facilitating the understanding of abstract and complex principles. Using machine learning algorithms, AI systems can process a large amount of data related to student learning and, based on this, identify patterns that are difficult for an observer-educator to immediately understand. This allows students to correctly and fully convey the concepts of the laws of physics and their application.

In recent years, foreign studies have observed the following main trends in the use of artificial intelligence in school physics education:

- virtual laboratories: using artificial intelligence simulations to create interactive virtual laboratories where schoolchildren can conduct experiments and observe physical phenomena. Such virtual laboratory works allow the safe study of complex or dangerous physical processes.

- visualisation and modelling: using artificial intelligence generators to dynamically visualise and create 3D models of physical concepts such as the motion of physical objects, electromagnetic fields, and quantum phenomena. This course helps students better understand abstract physical principles.

- interactive teaching systems: development of flexible artificial intelligence systems that monitor the dynamics of students' learning of physics, identify problems

in it, and offer personal explanations and practical tasks. Such systems help students consolidate their knowledge and develop skills for solving physical problems.

- **Assessment automation:** using artificial intelligence technologies to automatically check and assess physical calculations, laboratory reports, and written work. This allows teachers to spend less time on regular assessments of student performance and more time on individual support.

Integration with other educational technologies: Combining artificial intelligence systems with other educational technologies such as augmented reality, virtual simulators, and cloud computing. This will help create comprehensive digital ecosystems that will positively impact the effectiveness of physics education.

The trends discussed above show that artificial intelligence is becoming a modern, integral part of teaching physics in schools, pointing to the provision of more interactivity, individualization, and adaptation of the study of physical laws, phenomena, and processes to other technologies. are used [9].

The use of artificial intelligence technologies in physics classes has the following potential advantages:

- **increase the motivation of students:** interactive and attractive programmes and applications based on artificial intelligence can help students to be interested in physical phenomena and processes based on independent study and research by conducting experiments;

- **individualization of teaching:** the use of artificial intelligence makes it possible to create personalised educational programmes according to the level of knowledge and educational needs of each student;

- **development of critical observation:** in the process of using artificial intelligence in physics classes, students develop analytical and critical thinking skills due to the fact that they are forced to make independent decisions and solve problems when using applications;

- **increase of practical competence:** the use of virtual laboratories and simulators based on artificial intelligence allows students to gain experience and apply theoretical knowledge in cases where access to educational laboratories is insufficient.

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that research on the organisation of the educational process using artificial intelligence technologies in general secondary schools is one of the urgent pedagogical problems awaiting its solution [10].

In recent years, research on the use of artificial intelligence in teaching physics at school has been actively conducted in the following countries: the United States of America, China, Great Britain, Japan, and Germany. In these countries, the use of SI

in teaching physics is seen as an important step towards improving the quality and efficiency of teaching this subject in schools.

First of all, with the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies in teaching physics, it will be necessary to train and improve the skills of teachers who have knowledge and skills in AI and methods of using it in the educational process. In these processes, it is important to ensure the cooperation of researchers, education management agencies, pedagogues, and other interested parties who work in these directions, as well as bringing the necessary modern knowledge to the attention of future teachers and pedagogues. If necessary, necessary additions and changes will be made to the legal and regulatory framework.

At present, we can say that the field of artificial intelligence is still in the early stages of its development. Therefore, in order to use the potential of this achievement of science, science, and technology to change physics education in a positive direction for student education and upbringing and for the benefit of society, additional research and extensive cooperation will be necessary. [11-15].

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence technologies in the school physics course helps to eliminate misunderstandings between the student and the teacher and increases students' interest in science. This will create a foundation for them to be able to use science and modern information technologies wisely in the future. We can make the following four suggestions for this [11-15].

1. Creating a material and technical base aimed at studying artificial intelligence technology.
2. Training of AI specialists for advanced training courses abroad for study and internship.
3. Creation of educational, methodical, electronic manuals on SI technologies.
4. To promote this technology among schoolchildren and teachers by training specialists in artificial intelligence technologies and organising seminar trainings with their participation.

REFERENCES:

1. Physics. 10th grade textbook for general secondary schools/ K. A. Tursunmetov, Sh. N. Usmanov, J. A. Rakhmatov, D. B. Khomidov T.: : Republican Education Center, 2022. - 192 p.
2. Rustamovich, M. U. (2023). Comparative Analysis of 6th Grade Natural Science Textbooks of Uzbekistan and Turkey. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(3), 114-120.

3. Mustafojev O'.R. 6-sinf "Tabiiy fan" darsligida namoyishli tajribalarning o'rni va roli//Innovations in technology and science education 2:17 (2023),p. 253-261.
4. Daminov M.I., Mustafojev O'.R. Fizikadan maktab o'quvchilari uchun zamonaviy darsliklar yaratishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish//ta'lim sifatini oshirish: muammo, yechim va istiqbol1:1(2020), p. 683-685.
5. Даминов М.И., Каххоров С.К. и Мустафаев У.Р. (2020). Изучение основ нанотехнологий в школьной программе физика. Научные доклады Бухарского государственного университета, 3 (4), 320-324.
6. Jabborova, G. S. (2022). About operators in vector spaces and their main properties. Science and Education, 3(11), 17-32.
7. Jabborova G.S. Hayitova H.G. (2023) "Properties of the discrete Schrödinger operator defined on a triangular lattice" World Scientific and Methodological Journal of Research, 6(14), 118-126.
8. Mustafojev O'. R. (2024). The role of artificial intelligence in increasing student activity in school physics classes. Pedagogical Acmeology, 2(10), 218-221.
9. Daminov M. I. Mustafojev O'. R. (2024). Foreign experience and main trends in the use of artificial intelligence in school physics education. Science, Education and Innovation: Theory, Practice, Results, 1(1), 578-582.
10. Mustafojev O'. R. (2024). Forms, methods and means of activating the educational activities of students based on artificial intelligence technologies. Science, education and innovation: theory, practice, results, 1(1), 272-275.
11. Mustafojev O'. R. (2024). Using artificial intelligence technologies to activate students in 10th grade physics lessons. Pedagogical skills, 1(5), 134-137.
12. A. Sh. Rashidov is a person-oriented technology of education in mathematics classes. Center scientific publication. 2021 year. Number 3. pp. 68-72
13. A.Sh. Rashidov. Conducting practical training in mathematical sciences for students of social and humanitarian education. Science and Education #9. С 283-291
14. О.О.Халлоқова. А.Рашидов Пороговое собственное значение модели Фридрикса. Молодой ученый, 2015 №15. С. 1-3
15. A. Sh. Rashidov Interaktivnyye metody pri izuchenii temy "Opredelennyu integral i yego prilozheniya". Nauchnyye issledovaniya. № 34:3. С 21-24